

CLINICAL-LABORATORY EXAMINATION AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN WORKERS OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

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Annotation. the question of negative cases in the oral cavity of workers in the chemical industry remains relevant. it has been proven that the high prevalence of non-carious lesions of the mucous membrane of the teeth, oral cavity is associated with production processes such as oil and gas extraction, metallurgy, chemical production, baking bread and confectionery production. prevention and health of dental diseases helps to maintain the working capacity of an important part of the country's population - workers of industrial enterprises, especially since a number of studies reliably reveal the role of dental and environmental tissues in the general condition of the body [1].

key otters: industrial corrals, dental diseases, oil, gas, oral cavity

It has been proven that there is a high risk of occupational diseases among workers in the industry. this is due to the extraction of compounds of elements into the human body through the oral cavity. industrial workers are characterized by a high prevalence of dental caries and inflammatory periodontal disease [4].chemicals of the industrial air environment were detected in oral fluid, solid tissue of teeth, biopsy samples of the structure of the tissues of the oral mucosa. they increase the course of dental caries due to the exchange of calcium ions in hydroxyapatite crystals, chronic inflammation in periodontal tissues, violation of the integrity of the epithelium of the oral mucosa [6].but the chemical factors of the industry are the effect of workers on the oral cavity, the consequences of these effects have not been fully studied. given this, the need to continue dental, clinical, functional and microbiological research on this issue has not lost its relevance [2,5].the " navoiazot " enterprise was determined on the basis of a dental medical examination conducted among workers of the chemical production industry, the results of a special and additional examination of the oral cavity and the elimination of cocktail conditions from a sanitary and hygienic state, that there are unpleasant sanitary-hygienic factors in the cocktail conditions of workers, which will cause the emergence of a number of one of the main characteristics of oral diseases that occurs among employees of the navoiazot enterprise is that they have more oral

mucosa and parodont tissue jaroxatated. the most common of these are allergic stomatitis (44.5%), 5.7 times more common than control rice (7.7%) [3.6]. among workers, periodont tissue diseases characteristic of professional description or caused by the direct influence of harmful factors observed in the conditions of cocktails at the enterprise are 27.4% - 41.8%. in the control group, these diseases occur 2 times less (14.1% - 21.4%). it should be noted that the changes observed in the oral cavity are accompanied by the processes of redness, swelling, itching of the mucous membrane of the gums, tooth decay, aching of the tongue, tickling of the upper respiratory tract and frequent sneezing [1,4].goalin chemical industry workers there was a clinical-laboratory examination of dental diseases and the identification of modern methods of treatment.

Research material

Examination of patients-it sets itself the goal of choosing treatment methods by correctly diagnosing their diseases. examination maboynida should take a very careful approach to a change in the stream observed in the body of the patient. because this condition can help determine the etiological factors of common and dental diseases observed in the body. one of the main conditions for examining patients is the study of their complaints. the study of the complaint of patients is distinguished from the main stages of diagnosis of the disease. But to accurately diagnose the disease and choose the right treatment measures will have to take into account my general state in the patient's body. Therefore, when making a diagnosis, the methods of collecting general and special anamnestic data differ. "navoiazot" helps to determine the extent to which common diseases in the body of oral diseases occur among employees of the enterprise affect the organs of the oral cavity. because changes in the oral cavity can be namayon as one waist of the total comorbidities observed in the patient's body. in addition, the identification of general diseases in the patient's body will help me determine the indications and contraindications for the selection of anesthetics used in maxillary anesthetics, which the patient is planning to transfer to the patient. and the collection of special anamnesis sets itself the goal of studying the complaints of patients that belong to the facial jaw. this involves telling patients about their complaints, and additional questions are asked in order to know when they appeared, the cause and the characteristics of the discord.

One of the main reasons for the appeal of patients to the doctor – dentist khuzuri is pain. there may be pain: in dental diseases (caries, nocarious lesions, pulpitis, periodontitis), paradont (gingivitis, periodontitis, periodontoz) and oral mucosa

(stomatitis) sox, as well as pain can occur in the face – jaw. In dental caries and nocariosis, there is pain in the tooth socket due to external influences (mechanical, thermal, and chemical), and the pain stops when the effect is over. In pulpitis, pain is complained of for no reason, pain that occurs at night and worsens under the influence of external influences in the case of periodontitis, however, pain is complained of continuously, pain that hurts with a bite and worsens when bitten.

In the case of parodont diseases, patients complain of bleeding gums in addition to pain, twitching of teeth and, in some cases, tooth decay in diseases of the oral mucosa, patients complain of dry mouth, redness of the mucous membrane and the appearance of wounds, as well as unpleasant odor from the mouth. 1,470 patients aged 19-55 years and older who were treated were examined for oral diseases found among employees of the navoiazot enterprise. patients aged 19 to 55 years and older were considered to have a higher risk of chemical production poisoning. the age levels of patients are compiled according to the who classification (table 1). the age group from 19 to 29 was made up of 568 patients (38.6%), the age group from 30-39 was made up of 354 patients (24.1%), 450 patients were in the 40-54 age range (30.6%), and 98 patients were 55 years of age or older (6.67%).

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